

Deliverable D4 within 19ENG08

- Good Practice Guide on the calibration procedure for traceable mechanical power measurement based on synchronised torque and rotational speed measurement -

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Disclaimer

Any mention of commercial products within this report is for information only; it does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the partners in this project.

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1 Introduction

In March 2022, the European Commission proposed a “joint European action for more affordable, secure and sustainable energy” [1]. To make Europe independent from Russian fossil fuels, main goals are to boost energy efficiency and increase renewables. Wind energy has much potential to speed up this green transition. For boosting the energy efficiency of wind turbines, a traceable and comparable efficiency determination method for nacelle drive trains and their components on nacelle test benches (NTBs) is required.

The efficiency of electrical machines can be determined either directly or indirectly. The direct efficiency determination is based on mechanical and electrical powers, i.e., input and output power measurements. Whereas the indirect efficiency determination method uses electrical power and power losses measurements, i.e., summation of losses. IEC 60034-2-1 explains the test methods for the determination of losses and the efficiency classification [2].

Based on the direct method, a new efficiency determination method for nacelles on NTBs based on traceable mechanical and electrical power measurement has been developed in the EMPIR project 19ENG08 “Traceable mechanical and electrical power measurement for efficiency determination of wind turbines” short WindEFCY.

In the previous EMPIR 14IND14 project “Torque measurement in the MN·m range”, the calibration of the NTB’s torque transducer using an integrated Torque Transfer Standard (TTS) directly on NTBs has been introduced. Here in the work package 2 (WP2) of the follow up project WindEFCY, the previously developed torque calibration method is extended with rotational speed measurement method, and a detailed procedure for traceable rotational mechanical power measurement are presented in this good practice guide.

The aim of this Good Practice Guide is to achieve traceable mechanical power in NTBs through methods for the interpretation of traceability sources and realization of measurement procedures. In section 2-3, the calibration procedure using transfer standards and the corresponding measurement uncertainty estimation are introduced as important background information for a comprehensive understanding of measurement traceability on NTBs. In section 4, an instruction is given describing the implementation of the acquired calibration results (certificates) for future measurement campaign.

1.1 Glossary

- Calibration: operation that, under specified conditions, in a first step, establishes a relation between the quantity values with measurement uncertainties provided by measurement standards and corresponding indications with associated measurement uncertainties and, in a second step, uses this information to establish a relation for obtaining a measurement result from an indication (VIM 2.39).
- Transfer standard: calibrated and well-studied transducer, which is used to trace in-situ measurement to the national standard.
- In-situ calibration: it relies on the comparison between a test bench sensor with a transfer standard directly during operation. The transfer standard is usually a state of the art reference sensor that has been calibrated and well-studied in a national metrology institute (NMI) with proved measurement uncertainty.
- Zero signal: offset value of a measuring device in non-loaded condition. The zero signal is used to tare all measurement signals of the following load cycle.
- Measurement uncertainty (MU): non-negative parameter characterising the dispersion of the quality values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used (VIM 2.26).
- Traceability: it involves verifying the accuracy of a measurement by comparing it to a higher calibration reference standard, thus accounting for all uncertainties and ensuring a precise representation of the object being measured

- Nacelle test bench: a facility used to test a wind turbine and the components, simulating real-world conditions to assess performance, durability, and safety before deployment.

1.2 Symbols and their meaning

Important symbols and their meaning regarding the efficiency determination on NTBs are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptions of the measurement parameters

Symbol	Designation	Unit
	AE = Displayed unit of the output signal (e.g. N m, mV/V, V, Hz)	AE
M_k	Calibration torque	N m
Y	Calibration result	N m
I	Direct torque reading from the device	N m
I_0	Zero torque offset determined under rotation during calibration	N m
X_i	Torque measurement value after taring	N m
$b'(M_k, n)$	Repeatability at calibration torque M_k	AE
$q(M_k, n)$	Indication deviation at calibration torque M_k and n	AE
$f_0(n)$	Zero point deviation	AE
$h(M_k, n)$	Reversibility of the torque measuring device at the calibration torque M_k	AE
$s(M_k)$	Instability at the calibration torque M_k	AE
N	the number of repeated load cycles	-
$q_{\%}(M_k, n)$	Relative indication deviation at calibration torque M_k and n	%
$e_{P_{me}\%}$	The relative averaging error using the adapted expression of mechanical power determination.	%
M	Torque measurement result	N m
M_s	Measured torque value before taring	N m
M_{zero}	Averaging of measured torque zero signals	N m
n	Shaft rotational speed	min ⁻¹
N_{res}	Number of shaft revolutions used for power calculation	-
N_{zero}	Number of angle positions measured for static zero offset	-
P_{in}	System input power	W
P_{me}	Mechanical power	W
$P_{me,ad}$	Mechanical power calculated using the adapted expression	W
T_{me}	Mechanical power measurement interval	s
U	Absolute expanded uncertainty ($k=2$)	-
W	Relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$)	-

2 Measurement Set-up

In contrast to conducting efficiency measurements in the field, evaluating the efficiency of a wind turbine on a NTB presents certain advantages, including enhanced reproducibility and reduced time demands. Furthermore, the availability of substantial space allows for the installation of necessary sensors at multiple strategic measurement points. Hereafter, this guide provides a short description of a NTB configuration furnished with appropriately calibrated sensors.

2.1 NTB Set-up

As depicted in Figure 1, an NTB commonly features an electrical motor serving as the primary driving mechanism to generate dynamic torque loads and rotational speeds. The maximum torque that can be applied at the test bench typically falls within the MN m range, with a rotational speed lower than 30 min^{-1} . Positioned between the prime mover and the device under test (DUT), the non-torque loading unit (NTL) unit constitutes a servo hydraulic system that imparts forces and bending moments to the drivetrain.

Figure 1: NTB at CWD of RWTH University including FVA nacelle. Modified based on [3].

In Figure 2, the entire configuration, including all specified measurement locations, is depicted in the form of an equivalent circuit diagram. When it comes to assessing system efficiency, the mechanical input power can be quantified at the low-speed shaft (LSS), while electrical power measurements are taken at the grid output. In the case of component efficiency evaluations, such as for the gearbox (provided the DUT is not a direct-drive nacelle), the converter, and the transformer, supplementary measurement points can be positioned at the high-speed shaft (HSS) following the gearbox, as well as at the generator and converter outputs.

*Currents and Voltages are effective values of the 3 phase system

Figure 2: Equivalent circuit diagram of the test set-up with full size converter at RWTH Aachen.

If the torque measurement device is located not directly at the DUT input, but with the NTL in between, the friction losses caused by the NTL unit should be compensated during the calibration.

2.2 Measurement sensors and calibration

The NTBs are usually equipped with a diverse array of sensors designed to monitor various measurement parameters. The most relevant sensors for efficiency determination are mainly the torque and the rotational speed sensors used for mechanical input power.

2.2.1 In-situ calibration

To enhance measurement precision and assess the quality of measurements, it is essential that all sensors utilized for determining efficiency undergo accurate calibration procedures to establish a traceability link to national standards. In this specific scenario, the preferred method is referred to as "in-situ calibration." In-situ calibration entails a direct comparison between an NTB sensor and a transfer standard while the sensors are actively in use. The transfer standard typically comprises a state-of-the-art reference sensor, which has undergone meticulous calibration and thorough examination at a National Metrology Institute (NMI) or an Accredited Calibration Laboratory, thereby demonstrating well-documented measurement uncertainty.

By introducing the additional transfer standard into the test setup, the standalone reference system concurrently measures the signal alongside the NTB's existing measurement system for calibration purposes. In comparison to the alternative of removing NTB sensors and sending them to an external laboratory for calibration (external calibration), the in-situ calibration method offers several advantages:

- Calibration takes place in real-world conditions, encompassing factors such as temperature variations, friction loss (in torque measurement), parasitic loads, and electromagnetic compatibility (EMC).
- Simultaneous calibration of both mechanical and electrical sensors within a single measurement campaign.
- Calibration extends beyond individual sensors to encompass the entire measurement chain, including signal transmission and data processing.

2.2.2 Mechanical power transfer standard

The transfer standard used for in-situ calibration consists of a traceable measuring chain comprising an amplifier, torque transducer, and rotational speed sensor. An integrated system is illustrated in Figure 3. The traceability of the rotational speed measurement is described in D2 WindEFCY project: Report for traceable rotational speed measurement [4] and that of the torque measurement is outlined in D3 WindEFCY project: Report for traceable torque measurement [5].

A typical value for the expected extended uncertainty of the torque measurement of the transfer standard is around 0.1 %, while the extended uncertainty for rotational speed measurement is approximately 0.02 % at a rotational speed of 4.5 min⁻¹. These values serve as benchmarks for ensuring accurate and reliable in-situ calibration procedures.

Figure 3: The transfer standard for mechanical power measurement consisting of a 5 MN m TTS and an inclinometer used in the project to calibrate mechanical power measurement in NTBs as an example.

2.2.3 Data acquisition and synchronisation

For data acquisition and synchronisation, the ideal scenario is to capture data from both the transfer standard and NTB channels simultaneously. This simultaneous measurement is essential to guarantee precise efficiency, minimizing any time misalignment between the parameters. The fundamental principle of synchronisation is further detailed in [6], and you can find a summary of commonly suitable digital connections in Table 2.

To maintain consistency and accuracy, it is essential to configure all channels with the same filter settings and sampling rates. Typical practical settings include a 150 Hz low-pass filter and a 300 Hz sampling rate. These settings help ensure uniformity and reliable data acquisition.

Table 2: Overview of commonly used synchronisation technologies

Synchronisation technology	Ethernet (NTP)	Ethernet (PTPv2)	IRIG-B	EtherCAT	IEEE1394b FireWire
Accuracy	1 ms to 50 ms	< 1 μ s	< 1 ms to 100 ns	< 1 μ s	< 1 μ s
Wireless connection	Possible	Possible	Possible	n/a	n/a

As in the signal evaluation process in subsection 3.1.5, the mechanical power is determined over several number of shaft revolutions. All the listed synchronization technologies have neglectable accuracies compared to the averaging interval, and therefore suitable for synchronizing mechanical and electrical power assessment within the test bench.

Alternatively, if achieving simultaneous digital data acquisition from all channels is not feasible, synchronisation can still be accomplished during post-processing. It is crucial, in this case, to ensure that at a minimum, the filter settings of the various systems are consistent. Once this is established, data synchronisation can be achieved visually by using an artificially generated impulse or through mathematical techniques like cross-correlation. However, it is important to consider the potential variations in clock speeds among different data acquisition systems. Therefore, an uncertainty analysis of the synchronisation process should also be conducted in such cases to ensure data integrity and accuracy.

2.2.4 Calibration interval

The calibration certificate remains valid for up to 26 months, but shorter calibration intervals can be beneficial in certain cases. These include maintaining traceability or complying with specific quality assurance standards. Recalibration of the torque measuring device is necessary if

- changes have been made to the set-up of the drive train on the test bench side,
- changes in the measuring device's set-up have been made,

- the measuring device has experienced an overload surpassing the magnitude of the overload applied during the preloading,
- the measuring device was disassembled.

3 In-situ calibration procedure in the test bench

The torque calibration procedure is based on the German standard for static torque calibration *DIN 51309: material testing machines – calibration of static torque measuring devices*. It was adapted and mixed with *ISO 7500-1: Metallic materials - Calibration and verification of static uniaxial testing machines Part 1: Tension/compression testing machines* to encounter the challenges using a transfer standard under rotatory condition.

The European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET) has published a guideline on the calibration of angular encoders [7]. For the calibration of the speed measurement, there is currently no specific standard directly applicable for NTBs.

The measuring devices in a test bench consists of several components including the display unit, cables for the electrical connection and a data acquisition system (DAQ). All important parts of the torque measuring device shall be labelled uniquely and clearly and shall not be changed after calibration. This is also a reason for carrying out the in-situ calibration, as the external calibration would demand that the whole DAQ unit would be together with the sensor under calibration, or it would be necessary to evaluate the influences of a different DAQ unit other than the NTB.

It is a step-by-step calibration, mainly for torque, the selected points of the range should be well distributed within the minimum and maximum according to operating range of DUT. This range of the used DUT should be representative for any DUTs tested on the test bench (wide operating range).

3.1 Torque calibration

The calibration of torque measuring devices in test benches is carried out at nearly stationary torque conditions under continuous constant rotational speed ($n = const$). Small accelerations and braking as part of the control are considered stationary states once a plateau can be identified in the load profile. Measurements are always taken at the same operating point for each calibration torque, with the signal from the NTB (I_{K_NTB}) being the one to be stabilized in the target value (M_k) and the variations are taken from the TTS readout (I_{K_TTS}).

If the user of the NTB does not demand for calibration in both directions, in most cases, the NTB torque measuring device is only calibrated in the main operating direction of the test bench. This main direction of rotation should always be measured as a clockwise torque.

No additional non torque loads (parasitic loads induced by the uneven wind-field) may be applied during the calibration process. A self-weight compensation of the drive train or a simulation of the rotor self-weight is permissible insofar as this is not dependent on the test object. In most test benches, the torque measurement does not experience any non torque loads due to its positioning. A torque calibration without additional loads is thus closest to the intended purpose and thus fulfils the purpose of a calibration.

During the calibration of the torque signal, it is important also to record data from the speed measurement in order to serve both as a nominal reference and as a checking of the stability of the plateau (no big accelerations).

3.1.1 Load cycle

A torque measuring device can be calibrated separately for multiple measurement ranges, with a minimum of five torque points equally distributed within each range. The sequence of measurement points between a start and finish at zero is called “measurement series”, and that must be combined with the speed range possibilities. A group (or block) of measurement series is called “loading Sequence”. The torque value at each measurement point is called target torque value M_k .

In the beginning of each measurement series there are recorded the initial zeros, and in the end of the measurement series, there are recorded the final zeros.

In Figure 4, there is an example calibration sequence consisting of 5 measurement series, each measured at a different rotational speed plateau. This calibration sequence must be repeated at least twice, gathering at least 3 repeated series at each rotational speed plateau. This combination allows the user to calculate the following parameters:

- Initial zero (offset)
- Variation of zero within a measurement series
- Variation of torque readings for the loading repetitions under same torque point and same speed plateau (Repeatability)
- Reversibility of readings for each torque point at each rotational speed
- Deviation of indication between TTS and NTB torque measurements

Figure 4: Example of a calibration loading sequence that contains five measurement series (S1 to S5), each series with a certain speed plateau and increasing and decreasing applications.

3.1.2 Temperature equalisation

Prior to calibrating the torque measuring device in the test bench, all electrical components, such as amplifiers, cables, and strain gauges, are to be heated up. For this purpose, the measuring devices installed in the test bench are applied with supply voltage until thermal equilibrium between torque measuring devices and environment has been reached. It is not necessary to warm up the engine and generator (resistance increases as the temperature rises), as well as the mechanical components along the drive train, such as bearings and possible gearboxes, before each load cycle, as the warm-up process is lengthy, and the resulting thermal equilibrium is very unstable. These thermal effects are only indirectly considered through measurements in different thermal states and the subsequent determination of repeatability and reproducibility. However, the temperature and especially the influence of the relative air humidity on the torque transfer standard should be determined and corrected accordingly [8]. To do this, the temperature and the relative air humidity must be measured in the vicinity of the torque transfer standard (ideally at the location of the strain gauges) and the measurement signal corrected as follows:

$$I(M_K, n) = I(M_K) - C_{rH} \cdot \Delta rH - C_t \cdot \Delta t \quad (1)$$

3.1.3 Preloading

Before each loading sequence, the torque measuring devices must be preloaded for about five minutes in the calibration direction with the nominal torque. The purpose of preloading is to release the sensor body from the remanence influence, which indicates the remaining deformation and stress due to previous loading. Remanence is particularly present when the transducer has previously been loaded in the opposite direction, through rotated installation, a targeted anti-clockwise load, as is the case with static calibrations, or through an emergency stop on the test bench.

Ideally, there should be no stop between preloading and the actual measurement. After each emergency stop, a preload with nominal torque in the direction of rotation must also be carried out before further measurements can be taken. The zero signal used for taring should only be determined after preloading. If a preload cannot be performed, the remanence must be regarded as a further contribution to the overall measurement uncertainty. Typically, an initial preloading is executed when the set-up is put into operation.

3.1.4 Zero signal determination $I_0(n)$

For an in-situ torque calibration, the zeros of the torque signals (also called offset) are to be determined under rotation at different speeds n with no additional load applied. This takes place at the beginning of each Measurement Series in the defined speed level n with the control parameters used and control to zero torque at the NTB. This type of zero signal determination is called rotational zero signal determination at different rotational speeds $I_0(n)$, and it is necessary for torque calibration under rotation since the friction losses in bearings and gearboxes depend on the rotational speed.

A statement about the long-term drift of a torque measuring device can also be made based on consistently carried out zero signals. Even being the rotating zero the one to be considered as I_0 , it is also important to record the static zero variation in the beginning and in the end of the load sequence.

The corrected displayed value $X_f(M_k, n)$, accounting for the zero signal at the specified calibration torque, is obtained by taking the difference between the loaded condition indication $I_f(M_k, n)$ and the unloaded condition indication $I_0(n)$ prior to commencing the measurement series at constant rotational speed. At the start of each measurement series, the indication should not be tared, but mathematically accounted for during the subsequent measurement evaluation.

3.1.5 Loading conditions and signal evaluation interval

The duration between two consecutive torque steps should be as uniform as possible. Measurement readings for calibrations in discrete increments should only be taken once a stationary state is reached. Changes caused by short-term creep cannot be separated from other test bench-related influences. The load step instability s is defined as the standard deviation $\sigma(M_k, n)$ of the six averaged torque values per torque load step and rotational speed. It considers the ripples in the torque signal, which is in general noisier in test benches under rotation compared to static calibrations. These dynamic effects are caused by the excitation (non-ideal sinusoidal magnetic fields and the general construction resulting in an air gap variance) of rotating electrical machines and lead to control instability. These control effects further increase the load step instability. The amplitude ratio of torque ripples can be minimised by signal averaging and low pass filters.

It is therefore mostly a behaviour of the test bench and not of the transducers, but with the in-situ calibration it is the only reliable way to check for that because both torque transducers, NTB and TTS, will be sensible to these variations. Once synchronization is guaranteed, the variation of the error between the torque signals M and I can be evaluated as an indication of this instability of the signals.

Figure 5 illustrates torque and rotational speed ripples with a 90° phase shift, as observed in the 4 MW NTB of the CWD at RWTH Aachen. To address the impact of torque ripples, it is advisable to calculate the average torque signal over a span of six complete revolutions for each operational point [9]. The optimal number of revolutions should be maximized while still maintaining reasonable measurement durations for each load increment, and the selection of six revolutions strikes a balance between measurement time and measurement accuracy. To quantify and account for instability as a source of measurement uncertainty, a minimum of four revolutions should be recorded.

Figure 5: Real measurement data from a test bench for wind turbine drive trains; here the instability in the torque as well as in the rotational speed measurement over six full revolutions can be clearly seen.

On the HSS, due to the occurrence of a substantial number of rotations in a brief timespan, it is not essential to average over a specific count of revolutions. Instead, averaging can be carried out over a predefined time interval of 8 seconds.

3.1.6 Evaluation of the torque measurement in the test bench

After performing the calibration procedure introduced in the previous subsections, the torque readings of the TTS (I_{K_TTS}) and NTB (I_{K_NTB}) are recorded for each calibration points illustrated in Figure 4. By taring the torque readings with the measured zero offset ($I_{0_TTS}(n)$, $I_{0_NTB}(n)$) at the corresponding speed steps, the measurement torque values of the TTS (X_{i_TTS}) and of the NTB (X_{i_NTB}) can be calculated. In this subsection, the evaluation of the measurement torque values to calculate the measurement uncertainty will be elaborated.

3.1.6.1 Adjusting the measurement torque values to the targets M_k

Different from a torque calibration machine, the torque load generated on the NTBs is controlled and influenced by various parameters. In practice, it is not possible to stabilise the NTB measurement torque value X_{i_NTB} exactly equal to the target torque value M_k , and there is always a controlling offset. For further analysing the calibration results with perspective of the repeatability and reversibility, the offset should be removed by following procedure in Figure 6.

The difference (d_i) between the torque signals can be considered as a reference for shifting. Theory is that, in reality, X_{i_NTB} and M_k are very close values, so that the absolute differences between TTS and NTB are the same around this target value:

- To shift X_{i_NTB} till it reaches same value as M_k
- To shift X_{i_TTS} keeping d_i for the X_{i_NTB}
- Procedure to be done for both increasing and decreasing directions in the measurement series and in the subsequent repetitions of the Loading Sequence
- The new values are defined but the symbols are kept as X_{i_TTS} and X_{i_NTB} (or M_k)

Figure 6: Adjusting the measurement torque values ($X_{i,TTS}$ and $X_{i,NTB}$) to the target values M_k .

3.1.6.2 Calibration result $Y(M_k, n)$

The calibration result Y is composed by the readings of the TTS at the target NTB (M_k) reading as described in the previous section.

The calibration result $Y(M_k, n)$ is calculated per torque load step M_k for increasing and decreasing loads according to (1) in the same rotational speed n . The mean value for the various repetitions of load cycle i is calculated by averaging the decreasing and increasing series of displayed values, while accounting for the zero signal

$$Y(M_k, n) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{X_{i,TTS}(M_{k,n}) + X'_{i,TTS}(M_{k,n})}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where

N is the number of repeated load cycles.

3.1.6.3 Repeatability $b'(M_k, n)$

For every calibration torque, the repeatability $b'(M_k, n)$ is determined by calculating the absolute difference between the maximum and minimum displayed values of the increasing series among the repeated load cycles (red circles in Figure 7). as per (2):

$$b'(M_k, n) = |X_{max}(M_k, n) - X_{min}(M_k, n)|. \quad (2)$$

where

$X_{max}(M_k, n), X_{min}(M_k, n)$ are the two measurement torque values at the calibration torque M_k and the rotational speed n measured among the repeated load cycles.

Figure 7: Example of a calibration Loading Sequence with the figural illustration of repeatability $b'(M_K, n)$ in red circles, zero signal deviation $f_0(n)$ in yellow circles and reversibility $h(M_K, n)$ in green circles.

3.1.6.4 Zero signal deviation $f_0(n)$

The zero signal is recorded at the beginning ($I_{0,i}$) and the end ($I_{f,i}$) of each measurement series as shown in the yellow circles in Figure 7. The calculation of the zero signal deviation f_0 is explained in (3). It is the largest absolute difference between pairs of variables across all repetitions in a same speed plateau.

$$f_0(n) = \max_i |I_{f,i} - I_{0,i}| \quad (3)$$

3.1.6.5 Reversibility $h(M_K, n)$

The reversibility $h(M_K, n)$ is evaluated for every calibration torque and speed plateaus using (4). It represents the highest absolute difference between the indications obtained from the increasing and decreasing values at each torque step among the repeated load cycles as shown in the green circles in Figure 7.

$$h(M_K, n) = \max |X_{i_{TTS}}(M_K, n) - X'_{i_{TTS}}(M_K, n)| \quad (4)$$

3.1.6.6 Indication deviation $q(M_K, n)$

The deviation $q(M_K, n)$ between Y and M_K is evaluated for every calibration torque and each speed plateau using (5).

$$q(M_K, n) = Y(M_K, n) - M_K(n) \quad (5)$$

3.1.6.7 Instability $u_{in}(M_K, n)$

As elaborated in section 3.1.5, to quantify the operating point instability, the instability of the load point is calculated based on the standard deviation of the distribution of the averaged values in each six revolutions:

$$s(M_K, n) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=1}^6 (q(M_K, n) - \bar{q}(M_K, n))^2}, \quad (6)$$

3.1.7 Lookup table for NTB torque sensor and measurement uncertainties

The results of the in-situ torque calibration can be illustrated as a lookup table for the relative indication deviation $q\% (M_K, n)$ for every torque and speed plateaus:

$$q\% (M_K, n) = \frac{q(M_K, n)}{M_k} \cdot 100\% \tag{7}$$

Figure 8 shows an example based on the calibration measurement carried out within the project on the NTB at CWD, consisting of 8 torque load points combined with 6 speed steps. The black cells indicate the load points could not be reached due to the DUT power limit.

Figure 8: An example of torque in-situ calibration results as a lookup table of the relative indication deviation $q\% (M_K, n)$.

The measurement uncertainty of the relative indication deviation is estimated using:

$$W_{q\%} = k \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u_i^2 / M_k} \tag{8}$$

where

k is the coverage factor,

u_1 to u_n are the respective standard uncertainties relating to the parameters input from section 3.1.6 and also the information coming from external sources such as the uncertainty of the TTS, the resolution from both torque sensor. A list of possible uncertainty contributions is presented in Table 3. An example of the calculated $W_{q\%}$ is shown in Figure 9.

Table 3: List of possible uncertainty contributions to the in-situ torque calibration.

δX_1	influence of the torque measuring device's resolution r in the test bench on the zero value;
δX_2	influence of the torque measuring device's resolution r in the test bench on the indication;
δX_3	influence of the torque transfer standard's resolution r on the zero value;
δX_4	influence of the torque transfer standard's resolution r on the indication;
δX_5	influence of the repeatability b ;
δX_6	influence of the zero point deviation f_0 ;
δX_7	influence of the zero signal;
δX_8	influence of the torque transfer standard's zero signal
δX_9	influence of the reversibility h ;
δX_{10}	influence of the instability s ;
δX_{11}	influence of the measurement uncertainty U_{TTS} of the torque transfer standard;
δX_{12}	influence of the correction for environmental conditions on the torque transfer standard;

Figure 9: An example of the relative expanded measurement uncertainty $W_{M,cali}$ of the torque in-situ calibration results as a lookup table.

3.2 Rotational speed calibration

In NTBs, rotary incremental encoders are the most frequently used rotational speed transducers. To measure the shaft rotational speed, optic or magnetic incremental is used to induce voltage pulses as the shaft rotates, which 's frequency is proportional to the shaft rotational speeds. The signal is then processed by the data acquisition system, counting the number of pulses within the given time interval. Additionally, the rotating direction can be determined by generating two pulse signals with 90° phase shift, and by marking a start point as the reference position, the absolute angle position can be measured as well. Based on the measurement principles and linear behaviour, effects such as zero offset, hysteresis etc. are not necessary to consider in the procedure. Therefore, the calibration can be done by directly comparing the measurement signals of the inclinometer and the encoder at each speed steps. In subsection 3.2.1, an example of an in-situ calibration of the NTB encoder using an inclinometer as the transfer standard is presented. In the following subsection, an instruction for the calibration is introduced.

3.2.1 Performed in-situ calibration within the project

During the project, the challenge of developing a transfer standard for rotational speed measurement in NTBs is the lack of a stator (as with an encoder) at the rotor hub of the nacelle under test, where both torque and rotational speed are to be measured. This lack is due to the enormous height at the rotor hub and missing rigid structures. A stator-less rotational speed measurement can be realised by an inclinometer that measures the rotational angle of the drive train over time.

With the help of the static angular calibration and the deviation analysis, the calibration procedure was developed in [4] for the inclinometer, which is developed as a transfer standard for rotational speed and combined with the 5 MN m TTS and implemented on the NTB to establish a traceability chain of rotational speed measurement. During the evaluation of the measurement data, additional measurement uncertainty contributed by to mounting misalignments, eccentricity, dynamic effects, and the process of data evaluation were added to the static calibration results. In the end, the inclinometer shows a rotational speed related measurement uncertainty as in Table 4, due to the reduced measurement time at higher speed, the MU increases. [10]

Table 4: Total MU ($k=2$) of rotational speed transfer standard [10].

Rotational speed min^{-1} n	Absolute MU min^{-1} U_n	Relative MU % W_n
4.5	$8.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.018 %
5	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.020 %
6	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.024 %
7	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.028 %

8	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.032 %
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As the measurement uncertainty is lower for longer angle measurement [11], the rotational speed was measured for six shaft revolutions as for the torque calibration for a synchronous measurement of mechanical power. Based on the above-mentioned MU contributions, the traceability chain of the rotational speed measurement was established.

Afterwards, the rotational speed measured by the NTB's encoder was compared with the one measured by the inclinometer. Despite the great axial distance between two measurement positions, the result shows a deviation smaller than 0.009 % in all speed steps, which is smaller than the uncertainty of the transfer standard. Therefore, the encoder can be calibrated to have the same uncertainty as for the transfer standard. Furthermore, the rotary encoder generates pulses induced by magnetic increments under rotation, the signal frequency is directly proportional to the rotational speed. Its measurement principle indicates that its measurement uncertainty does not increase with rotational speed as for the transfer standard. That is to say that the 0.02 % MU at lower speed range can also be extended for higher speed range for the encoder. As the result, the encoder is calibrated to have a MU lower than 0.02 % in its entire measurement range. It is to be noticed that, although encoders are generally better suited for speed measurement in NTBs, the inclinometer concept was chosen in this project based on the need to combine with the torque transducer and the varying mounting conditions in the test bench. Although the calibration result of 0.02 % does not represent the best performance of the encoder, it is a verification traced to national standard. After all, compared to the uncertainty contribution of torque measurement, the rotational speed plays a minor role in the total uncertainty of the mechanical power.

3.2.2 Calibration of the NTB encoder using the transfer standard

The calibration of the NTB rotary encoder can be performed together with the previously mentioned calibration procedure for torque with various rotational speed steps. The measurement signals should be also averaged over the same integer number of revolutions for torque to eliminate the influences of the periodic oscillation and ensure a synchronised measurement for mechanical power determination. Thanks to encoder's straight forward measurement principle and linear behaviour, effects such as zero offset, hysteresis etc. are not necessary to consider in the procedure. Therefore, the calibration can be done by directly comparing the measurement signals of the inclinometer and the encoder at each speed steps. Similar to the torque calibration, the linear indication deviation can be used to correct the encoder. Last but not least, the uncertainty W_n is contributed by the uncertainty of the transfer standard and repeatability determined during the calibration using the same method as for the torque calibration.

3.3 Calibration procedure on HSS

The previously mentioned calibration procedures were focused on the LSS on the NTBs. The other measuring position for mechanical power is on the HSS, where the torque is significantly reduced by the gearbox and rotating at a much higher speed. The torque sensors used on the HSS generally need to cover a measurement range up to 100 kN m. Compared to the MN m range torque sensor on the LSS, HSS torque transducers in this range are commercially commonly available, and, thanks to the smaller size, they can be easily deinstalled and transported to calibration laboratories to perform external calibration.

As for the in-situ calibration and the to be described mechanical power measurement procedure on HSS, it is identical to LSS except for the signal evaluation interval. For a synchronised measurement, the averaging interval should be following the interval used for LSS, which is corresponding to an integer number of shaft revolutions. However, sometimes the HSS measurement is performed without LSS measurement, for example if the LSS measurement is not of the interest or the test bench does not have LSS sensors. In this case, due to the high rotational speed and thus large numbers of revolutions in a short time, the averaging interval may not be set for an exact number of revolutions but using a fixed time interval for at least 8 s instead. The 8 s was recommended by [5], to ensure the minimum measurement quality.

On the HSS more dynamics are involved compared to LSS. Since there is no procedure for calibrating torque transducers under such a dynamic load, additional tests should be performed to quantify the uncertainties. Due to the complexity, dynamic torque calibration especially for highly transient events should be investigated in future research and is therefore not covered in this current guide.

4 Good practice guide for test bench operators

In this section, the correct method to implement the received torque calibration certificates, as well as the detailed procedure for traceable rotational mechanical power measurement are presented.

4.1 Implementing torque measurement with calibration data

During the measurement procedure, certain steps and rules should be followed to ensure the calibrated torque sensors are working close to the calibration conditions. In this way, the measured trusted can be trusted to be in the guaranteed uncertainty interval.

4.1.1 Preloading of the transducer

Before conducting each measurement, it is necessary to preload the torque measuring devices with the nominal torque for approximately five minutes in the measurement direction. This preloading serves the purpose of alleviating the sensor body from the influence of remanence, which represents any remaining deformation and stress resulting from prior loading. Remanence effects are notably observable when the transducer has previously experienced loading in the opposite direction. This can occur through rotated installation, intentional anti-clockwise loading (as seen in static calibrations), or in the event of an emergency stop on the test bench.

Ideally, there should be no interruption between the preloading phase and the actual measurement. Following an emergency stop, it is also essential to perform a preload with the nominal torque in the direction of rotation before proceeding with further measurements. The zero signal used for taring should only be determined after the preloading process. In cases where preloading cannot be executed, remanence should be considered as an additional factor contributing to the overall measurement uncertainty. Typically, an initial preloading should be carried out when the setup is first put into operation to minimize the influence of remanence.

4.1.2 Measuring interval

Evaluating these dynamic effects necessitates continuous recording for each operating point. To ensure accurate measurements, it is crucial to wait until stable working conditions are achieved before taking values at a specific operating point. For the Low-Speed Shaft (LSS), torque signal averaging over an integer number of revolutions helps mitigate these effects.

On the High-Speed Shaft (HSS), as a large number of rotations occur within a short time, averaging over an exact number of revolutions is not necessary. Instead, averaging can be performed over a fixed time interval from 8 seconds.

4.1.3 Zero signal determination

After the preloading, the torque zero signal with no load applied is to be determined and subsequently used to tare the measurement signal. This is necessary because torque sensors, which are based on the measuring principle of strain gauges, always have an offset. This offset can change slightly due to the installation in the drive train and is position-dependent when installed horizontally. In order to obtain a suitable, position-independent zero signal, the zero signal is recorded in at least four static positions (twelve positions are recommended), evenly distributed over a full revolution of the drive train, and the mean value of the values is calculated as the zero offset. This signal offset M_{zero} needs to be determined at the beginning of each measurement day, then used in the post-processing to tare the torque signal M_s of all measurements:

$$M = M_s - M_{zero} \quad (9)$$

The accuracy of the zero offset directly impacts torque measurement. Having a greater number of measurement positions results in a clearer distribution of the offset at various angle positions, leading to a more accurate determination of the mean offset value. Figure 10 shows the torque zero offset measured at 12 evenly distributed shaft positions in three different days on an NTB. Although this

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measurement can be time consuming to perform on each measurement day, the risk of measuring only very few positions cannot be easily neglected.

Figure 10: Real measurement data from a test bench for wind turbine drive trains; here the distribution of the torque zero offset can be clearly seen.

4.2 Implementing the rotational speed measurement using encoders

Based on the measurement principles, two key factors are influencing the measurement accuracy of the rotary encoder:

- Firstly, to ensure the pulses are counted correctly, the pulse period must be significantly smaller than the measurement interval. To achieve this, the encoder should possess large number of increments along its circumference. The requirement on the exact increment number is actually depending on the operating rotational speed range: for LSS normally more increments are needed since the shaft is rotating slowly; on HSS there can be less increments as the shaft is rotating much faster. Generally speaking, the frequency of the encoder generated signal is expected to be in kilohertz range.
- Secondly, the number of increments along the shaft circumference should be accurately determined to ensure the measurement accuracy. If the rotational speed is not measured in full revolutions or transient speed measurement is intended, the increments should be evenly distributed as well.

To make sure the two criteria of the encoder are met, an in-situ calibration of the encoder using a reference system such as an inclinometer is recommended. In such an in-situ calibration, as the example presented in section 3.2, the transfer standard for rotational speed, the inclinometer, was verified in a calibration laboratory to ensure the performed measurements are traceable to national standard. In this example, although the measured difference 0.009 % is smaller than the transfer standard uncertainty 0.02 %, meaning the calibrated encoder is more accurate than the transfer standard, the calibration is still indispensable to establish the traceability chain for the NTB encoder by proving the measurements are correct.

4.3 Mechanical power measurement

Rotation mechanical power is the rate at which mechanical energy is transferred in a rotating system. In NTB, it qualified how fast the input energy is transferred by nacelle LSS (and HSS if applicable) into the generator.

4.3.1 The averaging error

The mathematical expression of rotation mechanical power is multiplying the torque applied to the shaft by the shaft angular velocity. The average mechanical power P_m within a measurement interval T_m is expressed as:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{T_m} \cdot \int_0^{T_m} M(t) \cdot n(t) dt, \quad (10)$$

where the transient value of torque $M(t)$ and rotational speed $n(t)$ are first multiplied and then averaged over the desired time period.

In practice, to minimise periodically recurring oscillations, torque and speed are separately averaged over the largest possible integer number of drivetrain revolutions. The actual number of revolutions should be as high as possible while maintaining acceptable measurement times per load step. So the adapted expression is:

$$P_{m,ad} = \frac{1}{T_m} \cdot \int_0^{T_m} M(t) dt \cdot \int_0^{T_m} n(t) dt. \quad (11)$$

Compared to (10), however, the adapted equation (11) for practical use is valid only for constant torque and constant rotational speed. If the torque and speed are coupled with dynamic ripples, the applicability of equation (11) can be quantified as the averaging error $e_{P_m\%}$:

$$e_{P_m\%} = \frac{P_{m,ad} - P_m}{P_m} \cdot 100\%. \quad (12)$$

Fortunately, the result of the work in [11] shows that the averaging error $e_{P_m\%}$ is generally small and negligible in most of use case. However, the error is tightly related to the ratio and phase shift of the ripples in torque and speed. It should be carefully considered particularly at high torque ripples. To perform this analysis, the torque and speed should not be only measured with the averaged value using a power analyser, but also the transient values in high frequency range are required as well.

4.3.2 Measurement uncertainty budget

The MUs of the torque and rotational speed measurements presented in Table 5 can be directly obtained after the in-situ calibration in section 3.

Table 5: Overview of calibrated MU for efficiency determination

Expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU) sources	Absolute quantity	Relative quantity	Distribution type
Torque measurement ($k=2$)	$U_{M,cali}$	$W_{M,cali}$	Normal
Rotational speed measurement ($k=2$)	U_n	W_n	Normal

Condition-dependent uncertainty presented in Table 6 fluctuates with changing environmental conditions and, as a result, is difficult to be included during the calibration phase.

Table 6: Overview of condition-dependent uncertainty for efficiency determination

Expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU) sources	Absolute quantity	Relative quantity	Distribution type
Torque zero offset measurement ($k=2$)	$U_{M,zero}$	$W_{M,zero}$	Normal

As the torque zero offset is determined as the average value of the static torque signal measured at N_{zero} number of different positions. The MU ($k=2$) of this averaging process is calculated based on the standard deviation of the distributions, reduced by the number of repeat measurements N_{zero} :

$$U_{M,zero} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{N_{zero}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{zero}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{zero}} (M_{zero,i} - \bar{M}_{zero})^2}, \quad (13)$$

and the corresponding relative MU is calculated with the reference of the current torque load:

$$W_{M,zero} = \frac{U_{M,zero}}{M}. \quad (14)$$

The other condition-dependent uncertainty comes from the operating point instability as mentioned in D8 WindEFCY project: Good Practice Guide for traceable efficiency determination of devices under test on nacelle test benches [12], as it mainly concerns the efficiency determination, the uncertainty source is not included here.

For implementation of the torque calibration results, the NTB torque measurement values can be corrected using the lookup table of $q_{\%}(M_K, n)$ as:

$$M_c = (M_s - M_{zero}) - \frac{q_{\%}(M_K, n)}{100\%} \cdot M_k \quad (15)$$

This corrected torque value includes an expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{M,cali}$ as determined by:

$$\frac{U_{M,cali}}{M_c} = W_{q\%} \quad (16)$$

Base on the basic equation for mechanical power determination:

$$P_{me} = 2\pi n \cdot M_c. \quad (17)$$

the expanded absolute uncertainty ($k=2$) for mechanical power measurement can be estimated as:

$$U_{me}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial M_c} \cdot U_{M,cali} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial M_{zero}} \cdot U_{M,zero} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial n} \cdot U_n \right)^2. \quad (18)$$

After mathematical conversion, the expanded relative uncertainty ($k=2$) for mechanical power measurement can be written as:

$$W_{me} = \sqrt{W_{M,cali}^2 + W_{M,zero}^2 + W_n^2}. \quad (19)$$

5 Benefit for users

By conducting the presented in-situ calibrations, test bench operators can benefit from knowing the deviation between their internal measuring instrument and a traced national standard and correcting for this deviation to obtain a more accurate mechanical power measurement result. By following this good practice guide for mechanical power determination, the mechanical input of DUTs can be determined more reliably within an uncertainty interval.

For the expanded good practice guide including electrical power for efficiency determination, deliverable D8 is available in [12].

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VII Acronyms

CWD	Center for Wind Power Drives
DAQ	data acquisition
DFIG	doubly fed induction generator
DUT	device under test
DyNaLab	dynamic nacelle testing laboratory
EMPIR	European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research
EPMS	electrical power measurement system
EU	European Union
EURAMET	The European Association of National Metrology Institutes
FhG IWES	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft - Institut für Windenergiesysteme
HSS	high-speed shaft
IRIG-B	inter range instrumentation group timecode B
LSS	low-speed shaft
MEMS	Micro-electromechanical Systems
NTB	nacelle system test bench
NTL	non-torque loading
NTP	network time protocol
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
PTP	precision time protocol
RMS	root mean square
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
WindEFCY	Wind efficiency

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